

Pilot silo with an automated biomass (forest biomass) supply system

Introduction

To provide a solution to the limitations in the distribution of forest biomass and to optimise the SALA FORESTAL SL Celrà production centre, the aim is to design and plan an automated silo that supplies forest biomass and decreases transport costs outside the current radial distribution area. Objectives:

- a) To facilitate the supply and use of renewable sources of energy such as biomass (forest biomass) and promote carbon sequestration in the forestry sector.
- b) Technology transfer between the Catalan Forestry Technology Centre (Centre Tecnològic Forestal de Catalunya, CTFC) and SALA FORESTAL SL, regarding biomass (forest biomass) storage and supply technologies.
- c) To design and plan an automated forest biomass supply silo.
- d) To lower biomass (forest biomass) transport costs from the SALA FORESTAL SL production centre to locations over 100 km away.
- e) Dissemination and promotion of the automated forest biomass supply silo

Lessons Learned

It can be concluded that the project is both technologically and financially viable. And the management and logistics improvements lead to a very significant decrease in CO₂ emissions into the atmosphere. On the other hand, the project provides a consolidated and stable method of consuming forest biomass, which revitalises the sector and brings a product that up to now has been undervalued into line with other energy sources. The project also helps revitalise the rural sector, origin of the raw material.

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

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